

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Oxidation of some Hydroxy Acids by Bis(2,2'-bipyridyl)copper(II) Permanganate

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The oxidation of glycollic, lactic, mandelic and nine monosubstituted mandelic acids by bis(2,2'-bipyridyl)copper(II) permanganate (BBCP) in aqueous acetic acid solution leads to the formation of the corresponding oxoacids. The reaction is first order with respect to BBCP. Michaelis-Menten type kinetics have been observed with respect to the hydroxy acid. The formation constants for the hydroxy acid-BBCP complexes and the rates of their decomposition have been evaluated. The rates of decomposition of the complexes show an excellent correlation with Hammett's σ values with negative reaction constants. Thermodynamic parameters for complex formation and the activation parameters for their decomposition have also been calculated. The reaction rate increases with an increase in the concentration of hydrogen ion. The decomposition of α -deuteriomandelic acid-BBCP complex exhibited the presence of a substantial kinetic isotope effect. With an increase in the amount of acetic acid in the solvent mixture of acetic acid and water, the rate increased. Addition of 2,2'-bipyridyl and acrylonitrile has no effect on the rate. Suitable mechanism have been proposed.

Kinetics of the oxidation reactions of aqueous potassium permanganate, a widely used oxidising reagent, have been reported by several workers^{1,2}. But the oxidation by permanganate ions suffers from several disadvantages which have been described earlier³. To minimize these, several permanganate derivatives, incorporating different counterions, have been used as oxidising agents. The oxidising ability and the selectivity of the permanganate ion seem to be dependent on the nature of the counter-ion^{2,4}. One such reagent is bis(2,2'-bipyridyl)copper(II) permanganate (BBCP), which is found to be a mild and selective oxidant and has been used in the oxidation of a number of organic compounds⁵. Hydroxy acids can be oxidised either like alcohols⁶, yielding corresponding oxoacids or may undergo oxidative decarboxylation to yield a ketone⁷. In continuation of our earlier work on the oxidation of some thioacids⁸, aliphatic aldehydes⁹ and primary aliphatic alcohols¹⁰ by BBCP, we report here the kinetics of oxidation of glycollic acid (GA), lactic acid (LA), mandelic acid (MA) and nine substituted mandelic acids by BBCP in aqueous acetic acid solution. Attempts have been made to correlate the rate and structure of substituted mandelic acids in this reaction. Mechanistic aspects are discussed.

Results and Discussion

The reactions are of first order with respect to BBCP. Further, the values of k_{obs} are independent of the initial concentration of BBCP. The reaction rate increases with an increase in the concentration of the hydroxy acid but the order is less than one (Table 1). A plot of $1/[\text{LA}]$ vs $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ was found linear (r^2 0.9998) with an intercept on the rate ordinate. Thus the reaction exhibits Michaelis-Menten type kinetics with respect to hydroxy acids. This leads to the postulation of the following overall mechanism (eqns. 2 and 3) and rate law (eqn. 4),

$$\text{Rate} = k_2 K [\text{RCH(OH)COOH}] [\text{BBCP}] / (1 + K [\text{RCH(OH)COOH}]) \quad (4)$$

Effect of temperature : The dependence of k_{obs} on hydroxy acid concentration was studied at different temperatures and the values of K and k_2 were evaluated from the double reciprocal plots. The thermodynamic parameters of the complex formation and activation parameters of the decomposition of the complexes were calculated from the values of K and k_2 respectively at different temperatures (Tables 2 and 3).

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE OXIDATION OF LA BY BBCP AT 293 K

[Hydroxy acid] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁴ [BBCP] mol dm ⁻³	10 ³ k_{obs} s ⁻¹
0.01	5.0	1.85
0.02	5.0	3.03
0.04	5.0	4.35
0.06	5.0	5.15
0.08	5.0	5.65
0.10	5.0	6.00
0.10	5.0	6.05 ^a
0.02	1.6	3.13
0.02	3.3	3.20
0.02	6.5	3.00
0.02	8.2	3.20
0.02	9.8	3.40

^aContained 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

Kinetic isotope effect : To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step, the oxidation of DMA was studied. The results (Tables 2 and 3) show that the formation constants of the complexes of ordinary and deuteriated mandelic acid are al-

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF BBP-HYDROXY ACID COMPLEXES

Subst.	K (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)				ΔH kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹
	288 K	293 K	298 K	303 K			
H	37.5	29.7	23.6	17.0	-42.4 ± 1.6	-109 ± 5.6	-10.1 ± 1.3
<i>p</i> -F	35.0	27.5	22.0	15.7	-40.5 ± 2.0	-103 ± 6.7	-10.0 ± 1.6
<i>p</i> -Cl	34.5	27.0	21.2	16.2	-38.9 ± 0.7	-97 ± 2.4	-10.0 ± 0.6
<i>p</i> -Br	35.3	28.0	23.5	16.8	-37.3 ± 2.4	-92 ± 8.0	-10.2 ± 1.9
<i>p</i> -Me	32.3	25.8	20.0	13.5	-44.0 ± 3.0	-116 ± 10	-9.8 ± 2.4
<i>m</i> -Br	36.8	28.0	21.5	15.2	-44.7 ± 1.6	-117 ± 5.4	-10.0 ± 1.3
<i>p</i> -OMe	32.0	25.5	19.8	14.0	-42.1 ± 2.2	-109 ± 7.3	-9.8 ± 1.7
<i>m</i> -Cl	37.5	29.9	24.0	17.5	-38.8 ± 1.8	-96 ± 6.1	-10.3 ± 1.4
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	38.0	30.0	24.6	17.9	-38.1 ± 1.9	-94 ± 1.9	-10.3 ± 1.5
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	38.9	31.3	25.3	18.3	-38.3 ± 2.1	-94 ± 7.0	-10.4 ± 1.6
GA	37.0	28.5	22.4	16.0	-41.7 ± 1.6	-107 ± 5.3	-10.0 ± 1.3
LA	36.2	27.5	22.0	15.8	-40.2 ± 1.9	-101 ± 6.3	-10.2 ± 1.5
DMA	38.0	29.0	23.0	18.2	-37.9 ± 5.0	-93 ± 1.6	-10.3 ± 0.4

TABLE 3—RATE OF DECOMPOSITION AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF BBP-HYDROXY ACID COMPLEXES

Subst.	10 ³ k_2 (s ⁻¹)				ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹
	288K	293K	298K	303K			
H	43.3	65.0	98.2	145	58.6±1.8	-68±6.1	78.7±1.4
<i>p</i> -F	33.1	56.2	85.1	129	62.7±1.6	-56±5.3	79.1±1.3
<i>p</i> -Cl	17.0	31.6	50.1	75.8	69.3±2.8	-38±9.5	80.5±2.2
<i>p</i> -Br	15.8	26.3	41.7	66.1	66.4±0.7	-49±2.3	80.9±0.6
<i>p</i> -Me	87.1	126	178	282	53.5±2.1	-80±7.0	77.2±1.7
<i>m</i> -Br	8.51	15.1	24.0	38.0	69.3±1.5	-44±5.2	82.3±1.2
<i>p</i> -OMe	144	251	363	525	59.2±2.8	-55±9.4	75.6±2.2
<i>m</i> -Cl	9.12	15.8	25.7	40.7	69.6±0.9	-42±3.6	82.1±0.9
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	2.14	3.89	6.61	11.2	77.2±0.9	-28±3.2	85.4±0.7
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	1.58	2.82	4.68	7.94	75.1±0.9	-38±2.9	86.3±0.7
GA	2.38	3.87	6.00	9.50	64.1±0.7	-73±2.4	85.7±0.6
LA	6.00	8.06	11.1	14.6	40.8±0.6	-146±2.1	84.2±0.5
DMA	9.62	14.6	24.0	33.3	58.7±2.0	-80±6.8	82.4±1.6

TABLE 4—DEPENDENCE OF THE RATE OF OXIDATION OF LA ON HYDROGEN ION CONCENTRATION

[LA] = 0.013 mol dm ⁻³ , [BBP] = 0.0005 mol dm ⁻³ , temp. = 293 K	[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)									
	0.05	0.07	0.09	0.25	0.50	0.75	1.00	1.25	1.5	2.0
10 ³ k_{obs} (s ⁻¹)	1.43	1.48	1.53	1.84	2.43	3.22	5.88	8.52	17.3	235

most similar but the rate of decomposition of the complexes exhibits a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 4.35$ at 298 K).

Effect of hydrogen ions : The reaction rate increases with an increase in the concentration of hydrogen ions (Table 4). A plot of rate vs [H⁺] is a curve concave to the rate axis and makes an intercept on the rate axis. The dependence of the reaction rate on the concentration of lactic acid was studied at [H⁺] = 0.10, 0.50 and 1.0 mol

TABLE 5—DEPENDENCE OF k_{obs} ON LACTIC ACID CONCENTRATION IN SOLVENTS OF DIFFERENT COMPOSITIONS

[BBP] = 0.0005 mol dm ⁻³ , temp. = 293 K	10 ³ k_{obs} (s ⁻¹) at % AcOH (v/v)					
[LA]	mol dm ⁻³					
	20	30	50	60	70	80
0.01	1.40	1.64	1.85	1.98	2.69	4.02
0.02	2.29	2.40	3.03	3.50	4.65	6.35
0.04	3.34	3.92	4.35	4.66	6.41	9.45
0.06	3.96	4.64	5.15	5.48	7.58	11.1
0.08	4.35	5.11	5.65	6.02	8.33	12.2
0.10	4.80	5.44	6.00	6.40	8.86	13.0
K (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)	28.3	29.0	29.7	30.4	29.2	30.5
10 ³ k_2 (s ⁻¹)	6.32	7.16	8.06	8.67	12.1	17.1

dm⁻³. The formation constant (K) does not vary appreciably with the hydrogen-ion concentration. This led to conclude that the change in the hydrogen-ion concentration affects only the decomposition of the complex.

Effect of solvent composition : Rates of the oxidation were determined in solvents containing different proportions of acetic acid in water. The rate increases with an increase in the amount of acetic acid in the solvent mixture. The results (Table 5) show that the rate constant of the decomposition of the complex increases with an increase in the amount of acetic acid in the solvent mixture of acetic acid and water. The formation constant (K) remains practically constant.

Effect of bipyridyl : Addition of 2,2'-bipyridyl does not affect the rate (Table 6). This rules out the possibility of a pre-equilibrium involving 2,2'-bipyridyl.

The oxidation of the hydroxy acids under nitrogen atmosphere failed to induce the polymerisation of acryloni-

trile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the reaction rate (Table 1). Thus a one-electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is unlikely.

A linear correlation (r^2 0.9806) between the log k_2 values at 288 and 303 K for twelve hydroxy acids indicates that all the hydroxy acids are oxidised by the same mechanism¹¹. The value of isokinetic temperature is 1271 ± 57 K. A linear regression analysis of the data for hydrogen

TABLE 6—EFFECT OF 2,2'-BIPYRIDINE ON THE OXIDATION OF LACTIC ACID BY BBCP

[LA] = 0.02 mol dm⁻³, [BBCP] = 0.0005 mol dm⁻³; temp = 293 K

[bpy] (mol dm ⁻³)	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.05	1.0
$10^3 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)	3.06	2.96	3.00	2.85	2.57	2.86

ion dependence reveals that at moderate concentrations of hydrogen ion ($[H^+] \leq 0.75$ dm⁻³), it has the form $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[H^+]$ ($a = 1.27 \times 10^{-3}$; $b = 2.5 \times 10^{-3}$; $r = 0.9969$) and at higher concentrations of hydrogen ion ($[H^+] \geq 0.75$ mol dm⁻³), the form is $k_{\text{obs}} = a + c[H^+]^2$ ($a = 1.1 \times 10^{-3}$; $b = 4.5 \times 10^{-3}$; $r = 0.9987$). This observation leads to propose that the reaction follows an acid-independent path and two acid-dependent paths involving singly protonated and doubly protonated forms of reactant as reactive species at moderate and higher concentrations of hydrogen ions respectively. Similar type of dependence of reaction rate on hydrogen ion concentration was reported in the oxidation of primary aliphatic alcohols by BBCP¹⁰.

The increase in the value of k_2 with an increase in the amount of acetic acid in the solvent mixture can be explained on the basis of the change in the acidity of the medium with a change in the amount of acetic acid. Wiberg and Evans¹² determined the Hammett's acidity function (H_0) for low concentrations of perchloric acid in a series of acetic acid-water mixtures. They observed that the acidity increases as the water concentration decreases. The reaction under investigation is an acid-catalysed one and hence with an increase in the acidity of the solution, the rate is expected to increase.

Correlation analysis of reactivity: A perusal of values in Tables 2 and 3 shows that the formation constants of the substituted MA-BBCP complexes are not much sensitive to substitution in the aromatic ring. Similar observations have been made earlier in the oxidation of the substituted benzyl alcohols by PFC¹³ and ceric ammonium nitrate and in the oxidation of substituted mandelic acids by PFC¹⁵. But the rates of decomposition of the complexes show considerable variation with the substitution. The oxidation rates of the monosubstituted mandelic acids correlate well with Hammett's σ values, with negative reaction constants (Table 7). Similar correlation has been observed earlier in

the oxidation of substituted mandelic acids by PCC¹⁶.

Mechanism: Not much is known about the structure of BBCP. In particular, the nature of the bonding of permanganate anions with the $[bpy_2Cu(II)]$ cation is not certain. However, in the corresponding halide complexes, it has been shown that one halide ion is joined to the central metal atom by a covalent bond and another by an electrovalent bond¹⁷. Based on that analogy, BBCP may also be represented as $[bpy_2Cu(MnO_4)]MnO_4$.

TABLE 7—TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF THE REACTION CONSTANT OF THE OXIDATION OF THE SUBSTITUTED MANDELIC ACIDS BY BBCP*

Temp. K	ρ	r^2	sd	l
283	-1.844 ± 0.13	0.999 2	0.013	1.64
293	-1.79 ± 0.032	0.995 4	0.032	1.86
298	-1.72 ± 0.037	0.993 6	0.037	2.03
303	-1.67 ± 0.03	0.996 4	0.027	2.21

*No. of compounds = 10; l = Intercept.

The observed Michaelis-Menten kinetics with respect to the hydroxy acid lead to suggest the formation of a 1 : 1 complex of BBCP and the hydroxy acid in a rapid pre-equilibrium. A hydrogen abstraction mechanism may be discounted in view of the failure to induce polymerisation of acrylonitrile and large value of reaction constants. In most hydrogen abstraction reactions, the reaction constants have small magnitude¹⁸. The presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 4.35$ at 295 K) confirms that the α -C-H bond is cleaved in the rate-determining step. The value of kinetic isotope effect is very close to that obtained in the case of the oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes by BBCP⁹. The substantial negative reaction constants together with the considerable amount of deuterium isotope effect indicate an electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state. The above results point to a hydride ion transfer in the rate-determining step. The hydride ion transfer may take place directly or may involve the prior formation of an ester. The intermolecular hydride ion transfer, giving rise a carbocationic intermediate, should normally lead to a correlation with σ^+ values¹⁸. Excellent correlation with Hammett's σ values therefore indicates ester formation prior to rate-determining step. This was further supported by the observed Michaelis-Menten kinetics with respect to hydroxy acid. The ester formation is not much susceptible to structural influence. Thus on the basis of all the above facts, the mechanism presented in Scheme 1 has been proposed.

Acid-independent path :

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